

The Effect of Safety Attitudes and Safety Climate on the Proactive Personality of Cabin Crew Related to Safety Behavior in Indonesian National Aviation Companies

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Abstract - Based on flight data in 2020, the large number of aircraft accidents that occurred during the last five years was caused by human factors, so this is one of the basis of research. The study was conducted with a total of 547 cabin crew from national aviation companies at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Jakarta. The data was collected through instruments on the questionnaire whose results were changed based on the Likert scale and tested first before data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method. The results showed that safety attitudes mediate the relationship of proactive personality with safety behavior, which means that the safety attitude created by aviation companies indirectly has an impact on the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior. Then the safety climate is able to moderate the relationship of proactive personality with safety behavior negatively, this means that the safety climate negatively influences proactive personality and safety behavior.

Keywords:- Safety Attitude, Proactive Personality, Safety Behavior, Safety Climate.

I.INTRODUCTION

Currently, air or airplane transportation modes are one of the transportation alternatives for people who want to travel long distances with relatively faster and more efficient travel times. However, based on data compiled by the National Committee for Transportation Safety (KNKT), there are several cases of accidents in this mode of transportation that occur in Indonesia and this is a disaster that should be minimized and avoided. As actors and managers of work in the aviation world, cabin crew have an important role in controlling safety and service levels in the aviation world. So that the safety behavior of cabin crew becomes very important for the overall safety performance of any airline (Kao et al., 2009).

Quoting an article from the Adisucipto Institute of Aerospace Technology entitled "Loss of Aircraft Control, Causes of Aircraft Accidents", one of the factors that contribute to the occurrence of aircraft accidents comes from pilots, namely improper decision making, failing to recognize aerodynamic stalls or spins, failing to maintain airspeed, not complying with regulations, not following applicable procedures, inexperienced, using illegal drugs or under circumstances drunk. The following are the factors

that cause accidents, where data shows that the main cause of accidents in Indonesia is due to human negligence, which in this study will be focused on the behavior of cabin crew.

In a previous study from (Ford et al., 2014), researchers saw that information about the safety attitudes of cabin crew was relatively unstudied, even though this is very important to better understand whatever interactions occur in the cabin, both between passengers and also the entire cabin crew and pilots who operate the aircraft. Cabin crew with a poor safety attitude cannot really implement flight regulations related to safety compliance and safety participation, and they cannot pay attention to safety practices. They will also not be able to handle their duties efficiently and effectively, which can lead to communication barriers between crews, the presence of service failures, and will pose other flight risks that will lead to reduced customers (Gabbott et al., 2011).

Then researchers also want to know and analyze about the safety climate in aviation companies. Where aviation companies need to pay attention to whether the safety climate has been met and carried out optimally. For example, management must emphasize safety as an important part of the company's operations, training all employees regularly to refresh and update knowledge, and the maintenance of equipment in accordance with safety standards. The term "safety climate" refers to the shared perception of safety policies, procedures and practices in the work environment (Zohar, 2003). The safety climate has a profound impact on the safety attitudes, safety values, and safety behaviors of all individuals in the organization.

Furthermore, researchers also wanted to find out if the entire cabin crew had a proactive personality, which is considered a tendency for individuals to take action to change their external environment, rather than being limited by the power of the situation (Bateman & Crant, 1993). Proactive personality is indispensable to the aviation world because cabin crew often face unexpected situations when a safety-related incident occurs that requires immediate solutions. People with a very proactive personality can deliberately and instantly change their surroundings, in order to improve their safety behavior.

Then, with regard to safety behavior, the researcher tried to analyze whether cabin crew had perceptions of individual safety behaviors which included behavior in the role (safety compliance) and extra-role behavior (safety

participation or proactive safety behavior). It can be seen whether they have complied with safety policies and regulations issued by aviation authorities and airlines which are a key element of the safety behaviour of the cabin crew role. Extra-role safety behaviors for cabin crew include promoting safety concepts and participating in their airline safety programs during off-hours (Chen and Chen, 2014). The goal is for them to maintain a high level of safety awareness and be able to assess and report potential hazards in a timely manner. In this way, it is hoped that some undesirable or unexpected events can be prevented or interrupted (Aase et al., 2005; Skjerve, 2008).

➤ Problem Formulation

This study tries to answer the following questions:

- Is there any influence of proactive personality on cabin crew safety behavior.
- Is there any influence of safety attitudes on the safety behavior of cabin crew.
- Is there a proactive personality influence on the safety attitudes of cabin crew.
- Whether safety attitudes mediate the relationship between proactive personality and cabin crew safety behavior.
- Does the safety climate moderate the relationship between proactive personality and cabin crew safety behavior.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Proactive Personality

Proactive Personality is an attitude that tends to take advantage of opportunities, dare to take action in deciding things and be active in doing the work done (Suryani, 2020). Proactive individuals are seen as leaders and act as agents of change (Robbins & Judge, 2013). They are more easily satisfied with the work and help others a lot with their duties, because they enjoy building relationships with others. Compared to passive personalities, people with proactive personalities will actively engage in changing unwanted environments, seizing opportunities, and taking the initiative to achieve their goals (Crant, 2000; Seibert et al., 1999). People with a very proactive personality can deliberately and instantly change their surroundings, in order to improve their safety behavior. Indeed, a number of studies have shown that employees' proactive personalities are strongly linked to their job performance (Bateman and Crant, 1993; Chan, 2006; Rank et al., 2007).

Chen and Kao (2014) found that proactive personality has a positive impact on cabin crew service performance. The relationship between proactive personality and service performance is also moderated by other social support and service climates. In addition, the level of adequacy in work and prejudice is also quite important when dealing with safety-related incidents. The proactive personality is considered as the tendency for individuals to take action to change their external environment, rather than being limited by the power of the situation (Bateman and Crant, 1993). There are several factors that influence proactive personality according to opinion (Bateman and Crant, 1993) including:

- Neuroticism, that is, emotional instability as opposed to adjustment.
- Extraversion, that is, a need for stimulus, activity,

assertiveness, quantity, and level of intensity of interaction between individuals

- Openness or intellect, which is a factor represented by flexibility regarding thoughts and individual tolerance, sensitivity, openness of feelings, experiences, and new ideas
- Agreeableness, that is, a factor represented by loving interpersonal recognition.
- Conscientiousness, that is, a factor that can influence the proactive attitude described by the level of organization, perseverance, and motivation with behaviors that are in accordance with the objectives.

The indicators used to measure proactive personality using the proactive personality scale that are included in the indicators according to Bateman and Crant (1993) in (Mahardika, 2020) include:

- Ability to see opportunities
- Demonstrate initiative
- Take action
- Persistent

Based on some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that a proactive personality is an attitude that dares to make decisions in doing something to change the environment. The dimensions on proactive personality used by researchers in this study are the ability to see opportunities, show initiative, take action, and be persistent.

B. Security Attitude

Safety attitudes reflect employee beliefs and feelings about safety policies and actions (Henning *et al.*, 2009). The safety attitude consists of four parts, namely 1) hardware safety and physical hazards, 2) software and safety concepts, 3) people and 4) risks (Cox and Cox, 1991). Safety attitudes have a significant influence on the safety behavior of employees, which in turn is very important in accident prevention. Employees with a good safe attitude will reduce the incidence of unsafe behavior, thus avoiding accidents that can be prevented and without the need for supervision (Eid *et al.*, 2012).

In the aviation industry, as frontline service employees, cabin crew play an important role in taking over the information passed on to flight deck crews, and in shaping key customer outcomes (Chang and Chiu, 2009).

In the approach of social cognition, models such as the Theory of Reasoned Action/Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 2005) and the health belief model (Rosenstock, 1974) recognize that personality traits can indirectly influence behavior by influencing behavioral or behavioral normative determinants. Evidence supporting the predictive value of these variables is found in several studies (Ulleberg and Rundmo, 2003; Ji et al., 2011, 2018a).

Based on some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that a safety attitude is an attitude that is as sincere as trying to avoid difficulties and trying to stay focused on their duties and responsibilities by upholding confidence in safety policies and actions.

C. Safety Climate

Law Number 1 of 2009 concerning Aviation article 314 states that every aviation service provider is obliged to make, implement, evaluate, and continuously improve the *Safety Management System* with reference to the national aviation safety program. What is meant by "aviation service providers", among others: air transportation business entities, airport business entities and airport operator units, aviation navigation service providers, aircraft maintenance business entities, aviation education and training providers, and business entities design and factory aircraft, aircraft engines, aircraft propellers, and aircraft components. The training that must be given to all cabin crew, namely: Course Introduction, System Management Overview and Fundamentals, Safety Culture, Safety Management System Framework, Safety Policy and Objectives, Safety Risk Management, *Safety Assurance*, *Safety Promotion*, *Safety Management System*, and *SMS Regulation and Examination*.

As an organizational variable, the term "safety climate" refers to the shared perception of organizational safety policies, procedures, and practices, within the work environment (Zohar, 2003). The safety climate has an important impact on a wide range of outcomes associated with individual work, including in terms of safety performance, subjective attitudes, personal well-being, and safety-related outcomes (Burke *et al.*, 1992; Nahrgang *et al.*, 2011).

According to (Neal & Griffin, 2002), the safety climate is the perception of employees on company policies, procedures, and the implementation of safety in the work environment. Meanwhile, (Winarsunu, 2008) describes that the safety climate is a perception of workers in management attitudes towards occupational safety and a perception of the extent of the contribution of occupational safety in the production process in general. Other sources mention that the safety climate is a psychological aspect of safety culture that explains the values, attitudes and perceptions of individuals and groups towards the implementation of safety programs within the company (Cooper, 2000). And according to (Guldenmund, 2010), the safety climate is the employee's perception of safety policies, procedures, practices, as well as all occupational safety interests and priorities.

Based on some of the understandings above, it can be concluded that the safety climate is the perception and psychological aspects of employees in company policies, procedures, and the implementation of safety in the work environment.

D. Safety Behavior

Safety behavior is behavior that supports safety practices and activities at work, where both of these things must be accepted by employees as work requirements to avoid accidents at work (Zin, et al 2012). Meanwhile, (Wardani, 2013) describes that safety behavior is a work behavior that is relevant to safety can be conceptualized in the same way as other work behaviors that shape work behavior.

Another opinion says that safety behavior is a systematic application of psychological research on human behavior on safety issues in the workplace. Safety behavior emphasizes more aspects of human behavior towards the occurrence of accidents in the workplace. (Syaaf, 2007) defines *safety* behavior as a behavior that is directly related to safety, for example wearing safety glasses, signing a *risk assessment* form before work or discussing safety issues (Setiawan, 2012).

Based on some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that safety behavior is a systematic application of psychological research related to work behavior related to safety as a work requirement to avoid accidents at work.

III. METODE RESEARCH

In collecting data, researchers use a direct method, namely field research by distributing questionnaires to a number of predetermined samples. Questionnaires are distributed to respondents online which are sent through the *Whatsapp* application. All respondents filled out a questionnaire and completed a *self-report* measurement online. *Self-report* research is a type of survey, questionnaire, or poll in which respondents read questions and choose their own answers without interruption. Self-report is any method that involves asking participants about feelings, attitudes, beliefs, and so on (Jupp, 2006).

The population in this study was all cabin crew who worked at Soekarno-Hatta International Airport Jakarta, Indonesia and came from several airline companies. Data was obtained as many as 710 respondents who participated in the study. The selection of samples in this study used a *non-probability* sampling method. The *non-probability* sampling method is that respondents who meet certain criteria have an equal chance of being selected as a sample. And the technique chosen is *purposive sampling*. A total of 547 respondents were obtained who were used as samples because they met the criteria predetermined by the previous researchers. So that a sample value of 77.04% was obtained from the data received by the researcher.

IV. RESULT

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Based on the following data recapitulation, it was seen that respondents with female sex were 54.3% (n=297) and men were 45.7% (n=250). Respondents with an age range of 20 – 23 years were the largest participants, namely 37.7% (n=210) and 24 – 27 years old by 24.5% (n=133). The average length of service as a cabin crew is 1 – 2 years at 56.5% (n=309). The rest have a service life of more than 3 years. When referring to the origin of the airline, the cabin crew who responded was Garuda Indonesia as much as 16.5% (n=90). Then lion air masakapai as much as 15.7% (n=86). Batik Air as much as 13.7% (n = 75). Air Asia airlines as much as 12.2% (67) and Citilink airlines as much as 11.9% (n=65). The rest are Sriwijaya, Malindo Airline, TransNusa and Airfast Indonesia.

Characteristic	Frequency	%
Age		
20 – 23 years old	210	38.70%
24 – 27 years old	133	24.50%
28 – 31 years old	110	20.30%
> 31 years old	94	17.30%
Gender		
Woman	297	54.30%
Man	250	45.70%
Length of Service		
1 – 2 years	309	56.50%
3 – 4 years	121	22.10%
> 4 years	117	21.40%
Origin of the Airline		
Garuda Indonesia	90	16.50%
Lion Air	86	15.70%
Batik Air	75	13.70%
Air Asia	67	12.20%
Citilink	65	11.90%
NAM Air	45	8.20%
Sriwijaya	43	7.90%
Malindo airlines	28	5.10%
TransNusa	25	4.60%
Airfast New Zealand	23	4.20%

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

B. Outer Model

Fig. 1: Outer Model Results

The criteria used in assessing the *outer model* are validity tests consisting of *convergent validity* and *discriminant validity* as well as reliability tests with *Composite Reliability*. The *convergent validity* of the measurement model is assessed based on the correlation

between the estimated item values (*loading factor*). Furthermore, in the analysis *convergent validity* gives information about the reflection of indicators that are most closely related to the research variables.

Variable	Item	Loading Factor	AVE
Safety Climate	IK1	0.863	0.743
	IK2	0.902	
	IK3	0.859	
	IK4	0.834	
	IK5	0.850	
Proactive Personality	KP1	0.829	0.689
	KP2	0.905	
	KP3	0.881	
	KP4	0.755	
	KP5	0.772	
Safety Behavior	PK1	0.904	0.841
	PK2	0.920	
	PK3	0.926	
Security Attitude	SK1	0.830	0.741
	SK2	0.876	
	SK3	0.918	
	SK4	0.815	

Table 2: Convergent Validity Test

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

Based on the results of convergent validity testing, it is proven that all indicators in this study are declared valid. This is because all indicators in each of the measured variables produce a *loading factor* value greater than 0.70 and an AVE value > 0.5. So it can be concluded that the entire convergent validity test is met (valid). Furthermore, the second indicator reflects a strong indicator in explaining the safety climate variable because it has the largest *loading factor* of 0.902 compared to other indicators in the safety climate variable. Furthermore, the second indicator reflects a

strong indicator in explaining the proactive personality variable because it has the largest *loading factor* of 0.905 compared to other indicators in the proactive personality variable. The third indicator reflects a strong indicator in explaining safety behavior variables because it has the largest *loading factor* of 0.926 compared to other indicators in safety behavior variables. Finally, the third indicator reflects a strong indicator in explaining the safety attitude variable because it has the largest *loading factor* of 0.918 compared to other indicators in the safety attitude variable.

	Safety Climate	Proactive Personality	Safety Behavior	Security Attitude
Safety Climate	0.862			
Proactive Personality	0.595	0.830		
Safety Behavior	0.641	0.730	0.917	
Security Attitude	0.566	0.801	0.739	0.861

Table 3: Discriminant Validity Test - Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

	Safety Climate	Proactive Personality	Safety Behavior	Security Attitude
Safety Climate				
Proactive Personality	0.622			
Safety Behavior	0.658	0.799		
Security Attitude	0.589	0.897	0.825	

Table 4: Discriminant Validity Test – HTMT

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

The two tables above present the results of discriminant validity testing using the Fornell-Larcker and HTMT criteria methods. The results proved that all indicators in this study were declared valid. This is evidenced from the AVE root value for each variable greater than the correlation of other variables. Furthermore, using the HTMT Ratio method, the entire correlation between

variables is less than 0.9 so that the validity of the description with this method is also met.

The next step after the questionnaire item is declared valid, reliability testing is carried out. Reliability testing refers to the value of Composite Reliability. Here are the results:

Variable	Composite Reliability
Safety Climate	0.935
Proactive Personality	0.917
Safety Behavior	0.941
Security Attitude	0.919

Table 5: Composite Reliability Test

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

Based on the table above, it can be seen that all the variables studied have a Composite Reliability value which results in a value of > 0.7. Therefore, it can be concluded

that all indicators used in the questionnaire are declared reliable or consistent in measuring variables.

C. INNER MODEL

Fig. 2: Hasil Full Model Research (Inner Model)

Testing of structural models or inner models aims to determine the relationship between constructs, significance values, R-square (R²), Q-square predictive relevance (Q²), and f-square effect size (f²) of the research model. Structural model analysis in this study used bootstrapping techniques in SmartPLS version 3.3 with a significance level of 0.05.

The structural model represents the relationship between the latent variables used in the study. The structural model in this study involves one free latent variable, namely proactive personality, one mediation variable, namely safety attitudes, one moderation variable, namely the safety climate and one bound variable, namely safety behavior. The following are the results of algorithm calculations and bootstrapping for each variable in the structural model.

The stages of testing the structural model (inner model) are carried out with the following steps:

	R Square
Safety Behavior	0.652
Security Attitude	0.642

Table 6: R-Square Values

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

Based on the results presented in the table above, it can be seen that the *R-Square value* of safety behavior is 0.652. This means that proactive personality variability and safety attitudes explain 65.2% of safety behaviors with

strong categories. Furthermore, the R-Square value of safety attitude is 0.642. That is, proactive personality variability explains 64.2% of safety attitudes with a strong category.

	SSO	SSE	Q² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Safety Behavior	1641	755.133	0.540
Security Attitude	2188	1155.141	0.472
Total Q ² = 1 - (1-R ² ₁) × (1-R ² ₂) = 0.757			

Table 7: Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

A value of Q² greater than 0 (zero) indicates that the model has a good predictive relevance value. A value of Q² on a safety behavior model yields a value of 0.540 > 0. Then on the safety attitude model produces a value of 0.472 > 0.

In conclusion, the entire model produces a value of Q² - predictive-relevance (0.747) > 0 so that the overall model has a good *predictive relevance* value.

Path	F-Square	Effect Size
Proactive Personality -> Safety Attitude	1.790	Strong
Proactive Personality -> Safety Behaviors	0.072	
Safety Attitudes -> Safety Behavior	0.117	Weak

Table 8: F-Square Results

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

The F-square value is used to determine the magnitude of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables. Evaluation of the size of the *value of f²* follows the rules below

- The value of *f²* of 0.02 – 0.14 is categorized as the weak influence of exogenous variables on the structural level,
- The value of *f²* of 0.15 – 0.34 is categorized as a moderate influence of exogenous variables at the structural level,
- The value of *f²* of > 0.35 is categorized as a strong influence of exogenous variables on the structural level.

Based on the calculation results, it can be seen that the influence of proactive personality on safety attitudes has a very strong effect. Meanwhile, the influence of safety

attitudes on safety behavior has a weak effect at the structural model level and proactive personality on safety behavior has a weak effect at the structural model level.

V. HYPOTHESIS TESTING

The value of estimating path relationships in structural models using *the bootstrapping* method. Looking at the significance on the hypothesis by referring to the value of the parameter coefficient and the value of the significance of the T-statistic in the *bootstrapping report*. To find out whether it is significant or insignificant, it is seen from the p-value *ort-value* at *alpha* 5% (1.65 one-tailed). The results of statistical estimates are described as follows:

	Coeff Std	STDEV	T Stats	P Values	Decision
Proactive Personality → Safety Behaviors	0.276	0.050	5.504	0.000	Accepted
Safety Attitudes → Safety Behaviors	0.345	0.049	7.107	0.000	Accepted
Proactive Personality → Safety Attitude	0.801	0.015	52.163	0.000	Accepted
Proactive Personality → Safety Attitude → Safety Behavior	0.276	0.040	6.910	0.000	Accepted
KP × IK → Safety Behavior	-0.094	0.033	2.870	0.002	Accepted

Table 9: Hypothesis Test Results

Source: Primary Data processed 2020

Hypothesis 1 tested is the influence of proactive personality on safety behavior. Based on the processing results as presented in the hypothesis test results table, it can be seen that the coefficient of proactive personality towards safety behavior is 0.276 with a positive direction. Subsequently, the *t-stat* values were $5.504 > 1.65$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.000 < 0.05$, so the first hypothesis was accepted. That is, proactive personality has a positive and significant effect on safety behavior.

Hypothesis 2 tested is the influence of safety attitudes on safety behavior. Based on the processing results as presented in the hypothesis test results table, it can be seen that the coefficient of safety attitude towards safety behavior is 0.345 with a positive direction. Furthermore, the *t-stat* values are $7.107 > 1.65$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.000 < 0.05$, so the second hypothesis is also accepted. That is, safety attitudes have a positive and significant effect on safety behavior.

The hypothesis 3 tested is the influence of proactive personality on safety attitudes. Based on the processing results as presented in the hypothesis test results table, it can be seen that the coefficient of proactive personality towards safety attitudes is 0.801 with a positive direction. Furthermore, the *t-stat* values are $52,163 > 1.65$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.000 < 0.05$, so hypothesis three is also accepted. That is, proactive personality has a positive and significant effect on safety attitudes.

Hypothesis 4 tested is the mediating role of safety attitudes from the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior. Based on the counter, the specific indirect effects value as presented in the hypothesis testing table, can be seen the estimated value of the mediation path coefficient of 0.276 in a positive direction. Furthermore, the *t-value* is $6.910 > 1.65$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.000 < 0.05$, so the fourth hypothesis

is accepted. That is, safety attitudes dictate the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior.

The hypothesis 5 tested is the role of the safety climate as a moderation variable between proactive personalities and safety behaviors. Based on the processing results as presented in the hypothesis testing table, you can see the path coefficient of moderation results of -0.094 in a negative direction. Furthermore, the *t-value* is $2.870 > 1.65$ and $\text{Sig. } 0.003 < 0.05$, so the fifth hypothesis is accepted. That is, the safety climate weakens the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior significantly, which initially has a positive influence between the two variables

For the evaluation of the effect of moderation in this study, a simple slope analysis (*Simple Slope Analysis*) was used to better understand the results of the moderator analysis. *Simple Slope* is recommended because graphs can visualize the effects of two-way interactions on the plot or flow that follows.

The three lines shown in the figure below represent the relationship between proactive personality (X-axis) and safety behavior (Y-axis). The midline represents the relationship to the average level of the safety climate moderator variable. The other two lines represent the relationship between proactive personality and safety behavior to a higher degree (i.e., an average value of safety climate plus one unit of standard deviation) and lower (i.e., an average value of safety climate minus one unit of standard deviation) than the safety climate moderator variable. As seen in the following figure, the relationship between proactive personality and safety behavior is positive for all three lines as indicated by its positive slope. Therefore, higher levels of proactive personality go hand in hand with higher levels of safety behavior.

Fig. 3: Simple Slope Analysis

Next, analyze the slope of the moderation effect in more detail. The top line, which represents a high level of construction moderator safety climate has a flatter slope, while the bottom line, which represents a low level of the organizational climate moderator construction, has a steeper slope. This is because the interaction effect is negative. As a rule of thumb and approximately, the high-level slope of the safety climate moderator construct is a simple effect (i.e., 0.276) plus an interaction effect (−0.094), while a low-level slope of the safety climate moderator construct is a simple effect (i.e., 0.276) minus the interaction effect (−0.094). Therefore, a simple slope plot favors negative interactions: A lower level of safety climate requires a high relationship between proactive personality and safety behavior, while a higher level of safety climate leads to a weaker relationship between proactive personality and safety behavior.

VI. DISCUSSION

This study has successfully answered the entire research hypothesis. This means that there is a positive influence between proactive personality and safety attitude towards safety behavior, as well as a positive proactive personality influence on safety attitude. Furthermore, the indirect influence of proactive personality on safety behavior through safety attitudes. Finally, the safety climate negatively moderates the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior.

- **The influence of proactive personality on safety behaviors**
Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it was found that there was a positive and significant influence between proactive personalities on safety behavior. This means that the higher the proactive personality of the cabin crew will have an impact on improving safety behavior. Practically speaking, the cabin crew's proactive personality on the symptoms that occur on board the aircraft during the flight will reduce unwanted things and have an impact on the safety of the entire cabin crew and passengers.

- **The influence of safety attitudes on safety behavior**
Based on the results of hypothesis testing, there is a positive and significant influence between safety attitudes and safety behaviors. This means that the higher the safety attitude of the cabin crew will have an impact on improving safety behavior. Practically speaking, the positive attitude on the safety that cabin crew have will have an impact on the safety of the aircraft during the flight. Cabin crew are also required to be responsive and concerned about symptoms that occur during the flight as a form of flight safety behavior.
- **The influence of proactive personality on safety attitudes**
Based on the results of hypothesis testing, there is a positive and significant influence between proactive personalities on safety attitudes. This means that the higher the proactive personality of the cabin crew will have an impact on improving safety attitudes. Practically speaking, the proactive personality of cabin crew also has an impact on safety attitudes. The cabin crew's personality will reflect the attitude when bad symptoms occur during the flight. Therefore, it is important for cabin crew to have a proactive personality so that all passengers feel comfortable and safe during the flight.
- **Safety attitudes mediate the relationship of proactive personality with safety behaviors**
Based on the results of hypothesis testing, safety attitudes mediate the relationship of proactive personality with safety behavior significantly. That is, the safety attitudes that airlines create indirectly have an impact on the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior. In other words, when you want to build the safety behavior of cabin crew with a proactive personality as a predictor, it requires the creation of a good safety attitude from the airline..

- The safety climate moderates the relationship of proactive personality to safety behaviors
- Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the safety climate moderates the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior negatively and significantly. That is, the presence of a safety climate is able to weaken the relationship of proactive personality with safety behaviors that initially have a positive relationship. In other words, a safety climate must be created in each airline and must be implemented separately from the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior because statistically if the climate moderates, it weakens the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study and the analysis as a whole, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Proactive personality has a positive and significant effect on cabin crew safety behavior.
- Safety attitudes have a positive and significant effect on cabin crew safety behavior.
- Proactive personality has a positive and significant effect on the safety attitude of cabin crew.
- Safety attitudes are able to mediate the relationship of proactive personality with the safety behavior of cabin crew.
- The safety climate negatively moderates between the relationship of proactive personality to safety behavior.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions that have been described above, the recommendations that can be given are as follows:

- To improve and maintain the safety climate during the flight, airline management needs to increase the commitment of management, safety communication, safety training, maintenance, equipment to the cabin crew so that the airline does not suffer losses or margin reductions resulting from the weakening of the cabin crew's proactive personality and cabin crew safety behavior.
- The need for a review of the relationship between age, gender and length of service and the behavior of cabin crew to what safety performance is lacking even makes the proactive personality and safety behavior of cabin crew that has been implemented by airlines in Indonesia. Therefore, airlines need to optimize the safety climate such as management's commitment to the importance of a safety management system, as well as periodically evaluate the implementation of cabin crew's proactive personality, safety attitudes and cabin crew behavior so that airlines can work optimally and as expected.
- To other researchers who will conduct research on proactive personality, safety attitudes, safety climate and safety behaviors, it is advisable to examine other variables that also have a significant influence. So it is hoped that these researches can be useful in providing input and recommendations to companies and the academic world.

IX. IMPLICATION

Based on the conclusions of the research results and the recommendations outlined above, the implication is a maximum proactive personality, and also a safety attitude must synergize with safety behavior so as to reduce unwanted things and have an impact on the safety of all cabin crew and passengers. In addition, airline companies must be able to create a safety climate so that companies are able to get rewards in the form of a better level of public trust. The roles of all layers of cabin crew are also needed so that the operations of the airline company can run in accordance with the company's goal of being a leading company and upholding safety values

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